

How to assess and analyse activity spaces of adolescents in urban neighbourhoods?

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Abstract. Neighborhoods shape health through physical and social attributes, especially for adolescents and young adults as they gain independence and encounter new environments. A growing approach to studying these effects is mapping individuals' activity spaces. The aim of this contribution is to present and discuss initial findings for a research project that investigates adolescents' activity spaces with a focus on understanding the relationship between neighborhoods and health. We assess and analyze the activity spaces of individuals aged 15-20 in Berlin, Germany, using a web-based PPGIS to map their monthly locations. Using the provided locations, we model activity spaces using established spatial methods and calculate spatial variables in order to characterize spatial features of the activity spaces. Cluster analysis will categorize adolescents based on their activity space patterns, revealing distinct groups.

Submission Type. Analysis, Case Study, Dataset

BoK Concepts. [AM3] Geometric measures, [AM5] Basic analytical methods, [GS3] Use of geospatial information

Keywords. Activity Spaces, PPGIS, Adolescents, Health Geography

1 Poster Submission

Neighbourhoods, defined as geographic units of limited size whose formation and transformation involve complex social processes, have both physical and social attributes that directly and indirectly influence the health of individuals. Adolescents aged 15-20, experience changes in health behaviours - such as diet, physical activity, and substance use including tobacco, alcohol, and other drugs

- and health outcomes spanning physical and mental health (Warner & Settersten, 2017). As a result of increased independence and mobilities and the exploration of new social roles and newly evolving social networks, adolescents spend more time outside of their home, typically with peers

Assessing and examining the influence of neighbourhoods on health presents challenges due to the complexity of the underlying processes. The geographical delineation and definition of "neighbourhood" have led to extensive discussion, with various mapping approaches proposed and debated (e.g., territorial vs. ego-centred neighbourhoods). An emerging approach involves the mapping of activity spaces, which refer to a set of geographically distributed locations that individuals connect with over the course of their everyday life. These locations are typically captured through methods such as (web-based) interactive mapping tools like PPGIS (Public Participation Geographic Information System) or GPS tracking (Hasanzadeh, 2022; Kestens et al., 2018; Simon, 2024).

However, a research gap remains regarding the mapping and characterization of activity spaces of adolescents and their local exposure settings.

The aim of this contribution is to present and discuss initial findings for a research project that investigates adolescents' activity spaces with a focus on understanding the relationship between neighbourhoods and health. More specifically we address the following research questions with this poster

1. How can activity spaces of adolescents be assessed using a web-based mapping tool?
2. How can they be characterized in space and time?

We assess and analyse the activity spaces of individuals aged 15-20 in Berlin, Germany. To do so, we developed an interactive web-survey using ESRI ArcGIS Survey123 to map their monthly activity locations from different categories (e.g., home, school, public places, sport). Additionally, we gather details about visit frequency at these locations, social connections, and the transportation modes used. Further, we collect demographic data such as gender, age, household characteristics, socio-economic indicators, and self-rated health. We extract data from ArcGIS Survey123 in csv-format and transform them into geopoints. Data cleaning and preparation processes include e.g., geomasking of home locations, validation of activity locations, deletion of incomplete entries. We recruit participants from various channels including schools and universities. Data privacy and an ethics agreement are carefully addressed.

We then model the activity spaces by applying different spatial methods such as the Individualized Residential Exposure Model (IREM) or a home range model (Laatikainen et al., 2018) using Python libraries. We calculate spatial variables in order to characterize spatial features of the activity spaces (e.g., size, centrality, compactness, average distances, standard distance deviation). Finally, by employing cluster analysis in R, we aim to identify distinct patterns and categorize adolescents into different types based on their activity spaces and associated characteristics.

After completing the data cleaning process, we obtained a total of 334 datasets with an almost equal gender distribution (data collection still ongoing). The mean age of the participants was 17 years. More respondents participated from areas classified as simple residential neighbourhoods (lack greenery, have lower status indices, and are prone to noise and limited amenities). On average, each participant entered approximately nine locations, with public places being the most frequently reported, followed by eating establishments and visits to friends and family. Leisure/hobby locations and cafés/bars were the least reported. A comparison across age groups reveals that as participants grow older, they tend to visit public places more frequently, while their visits to shopping locations and cafés/bars decrease. In terms of average distances, the school category had the largest average distance from home, followed by visits to friends and family. On the other hand, eating/drinking out and leisure/hobby locations were, on average, the closest to home. Additionally, as age increases, the distances between home and activity locations tend to grow larger.

The web-map tool for the data assessment allowed to capture the variety of activity locations via mobile devices and computer. However, some software bugs, which could not be solved by the tool provider, created unforeseen challenges, leading to a high demand for

support during the survey's completion. Nonetheless, the collected data is provided in a usable format and can be easily integrated in spatial analysis environments such as QGIS, R or Python.

The application of the activity space models revealed new insights into modelling exposure for a highly mobile and diverse age group. The advantages and limitations of different activity space models are discussed. Additionally, the calculated spatial variables offer a more detailed understanding of how individual neighborhoods are structured and the characteristics they exhibit. The online web mapping approach is discussed in relation to similar methods, such as Geographic Ecological Momentary Assessment (GEMA).

Data and Software Availability

Research data supporting this publication is not available due to sensitive data on human subjects (e.g., self-rated health, activity locations, home places). Code for the models will be shared via GitHub.

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